

Supplementary Figures for "Biophysical Variability at the Shelf-Break/slope transition: Insights from a High-Resolution Transect Experiment in the Southwestern Tropical Atlantic"

ABR2 - ST9 - MICRO
12-Apr 21:41 to 12-Apr 22:36

Figure S1. Location and RGB recorded just after the Multiple Rectangles Transect experiment between 21:41 and 22:36 April 12 of 2017 during the ABRAÇOS 2 survey (<https://doi.org/10.17600/17004100>). The red line in the bottom panel indicates the target depth of the pelagic micronekton trawl starting at 21:51 to investigate the organisms responsible for the acoustic "fish-like" echoes observed between 85 and 135m. The net had a body mesh size of 40 mm, a cod-end mesh size of 10 mm, and a mouth opening of 24 x 24 m. The fishing duration was approximately 35 minutes, and the catch consisted mainly of the larger Carangiformes (Jacks) *Selar crumenophthalmus*, *Decapterus punctatus* and *Decapterus tabl* and the smaller Myctophiformes of the genus *Diaphus*, *Lepidophanes* and *Benthosema*.

ABR2 - ST6 - MICRO
11-Apr 11:14 to 11-Apr 12:05

Figure S2. Location, RGB echogram, and current velocity data recorded before the MRT experiment between 11:14 and 12:05 of April 11 of 2017 during the ABRAÇOS 2 survey (<https://doi.org/10.17600/17004100>). The red line in the bottom panels indicates the target depth of the pelagic micronekton trawl starting at 11:24 to investigate the organisms responsible for the acoustic "fish-like" echoes observed around 240-260 m. The net had a body mesh size of 40 mm, a cod-end mesh size of 10 mm, and a mouth opening of 24 x 24 m. The fishing duration was approximately 30 minutes, and the catch consisted mainly of Myctophiformes from the genus *Lepidophanes*, the Scombriformes (Mackerels) *Pseudoscopelus cordilluminatus* and *Taractichthys longipinnis* and fish larvae.